

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART II. VELOCITY OF SAPONIFICATION OF THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF THE SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID.

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In order to investigate chemical activity of the chloro compounds as expressed by their velocity of saponification, a number of various substituted amides of malonic acid were made to react with standard alcoholic potash solution and titrated with standard hydrochloric acid at regular intervals.

The velocity of saponification depends upon the nature of the radical attached to the saponifiable imino(NH) grouping. It also depends upon the position of the methyl group with regard to the saponifiable imino group.

The investigations with regard to the above were undertaken with a view to correlate the chemical activity of these substances as expressed by the velocity of saponification with absorption in the ultraviolet. The velocity of saponification was studied with the help of a standard solution of caustic potash. The reaction which takes place can be represented as follows :—

(where R = phenyl, tolyl, etc.).

A weighed quantity of the chloro derivative was added to 100 c. c. of *N/1*-alcoholic caustic potash solution so as to make the concentration of the solution 0.05 molecules per litre. Ten ampoules, each containing 5 c. c. of the above reacting mixture, were put in an electrically regulated thermostat maintained at 30°, it being previously ascertained that the chlorine atoms in the compounds studied remained totally unaffected even up to 40°. (C. B., B, 24, 2994). At the end of each quarter of an hour, one of the ampoules was withdrawn and the contents titrated with a standard solution of hydrochloric acid (0.125*N*).

In Fig. 1 are traced the curves showing the velocity of saponification of (1) dichloromalon-diphenylamide, (2) dichloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (3) dichloromalon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (4) dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide and (4) dichloromalon-di-1 : 3 : 4-xylylidide. It will be seen from these curves that

the curve representing the velocity of saponification of compound (1) lies between those of compounds (2) and (3); and again the curve for the velocity of saponification in the case of compound (4) is situated much below the curves for 1, 2, and 3. It may be pointed out here that the general position and sense of the curves 1, 2, 3 and 4 is similar to those of their respective curves of their absorption spectra, (*cf.* Fig. 1 in each of the parts I and II). The curve in the case of compound (5) has got a peculiar position which can be ascribed to the presence of two methyl groups in the xylidide radical.

Fig. 2 shows the curves of the velocity of saponification of (1) dichloromalon-di-heptylamide, (2) dichloromalon-di-propylamide, (3) dichloromalon-*mono-p*-tolylamide, (4) dichloromalon-*monochlorophenyl*amide. A study of these curves will immediately reveal that the velocity is enhanced in the case of (1) where there is a heavy heptyl radical with an open-chain. In the case of (2) the velocity of saponification is reduced. This may be attributed to the nature of the comparatively light propyl radical. During

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to dichloromalon-diphenylamide, -*di-p*-tolylamide, -*di-m*-tolylamide dichloride, -*di-o*-tolylamide and *di-1:3:4*-xylidide.

a comprehensive study of the velocity of esterification as well as on the saponification of esters, Kellas has shown that the molecular weight as well

as the molecular volume of the radicals attached to such a reactive group, appear to be an important factor in the determination of the velocity of reaction (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, 24, 221). With regard to the curves 3 and 4 in Fig. 2, it will be seen that although their nature is similar to those of curves 2 and 1 respectively in Figs. 1, the velocity of saponification as shown by the former curves is different, on account of the presence of only one tolyl or phenyl radical in the case of 3 and 4 in place of two such radicals as in the case of 2 and 1.

In Fig. 3 are traced the curves for the velocity of saponification of the three derivatives of methyl malonic acid *viz.* (1) chloromethyl-chloromalon-diphenylamide, (2) chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide and (3) chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide. The velocity of saponification is reduced in all these cases as compared with that of the corresponding derivatives of malonic acid (*vide* Figs. 1, 2 and 4). This difference is in excellent agreement with the difference which exists between the curves of absorption spectra of these two classes of derivatives. (*vide* Figs. 1 and 4 of Part I).

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to dichloromalon-diheptyl-, -dipropyl-, -mono-*p*-tolyl- and -monochlorophenyl-amides.

The results of the measurements of the velocity of saponification are summarised in the accompanying (Table)

With regard to the saponification of all the substances mentioned in Table I. the results give merely the sum total of the velocity of reaction of two saponifiable groups. When we consider the mechanism of the saponification it may be apparent that the velocity of saponification will not be the same for each group in the molecule. It can easily be conceived that the saponifiable radical being fixed on the same carbon atom will have mutual influence on the reactivity of each other. Consequently, the rate of saponification must slowly change as one of the groups is gradually being saponified. This will be evident also from the nature of the curve which ascends steeply in the beginning.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to chloromethyl-chloromalon-diphenyl-, *p*-tolyl-, and *o*-tolylamide

From Table I it can be seen that when the nitrogen carries aliphatic radicals, the velocity of saponification is greater than when it carries an aromatic radical having the same number of carbon atoms. (*vide* curve 1 in Fig. 2 and curves 2, 3, 4 in Fig. 1).

When we compare the velocity of saponification of the chloro derivatives of the malon-tolylamides the augmentation in the velocity of saponification could be represented as follows :—

This difference in the velocity of saponification could be attributed to the position of the methyl group with regard to the saponifiable imino grouping. When the methyl group is very near the imino group, as in the case of *ortho* derivative, the velocity is considerably low ; but it is enhanced as the position of the group is receding away from the saponifiable -NH- grouping.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to malon-diheptyl-, diphenyl- and -di-*o*-, -*m*-, *p*-tolylamides.

In Part I it was stated that the more active the molecule, the higher is its absorption in the ultraviolet and that the absorption bands are shifted more towards the visible. The above fact appears to be substantiated by this comparative study of the corresponding curves for velocity of saponification on the one hand and for the absorption in the ultraviolet on the other.

Ramart, Naik and Trivedi (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1934, 1, 525) studied the velocity of saponification of the amides of the type,

TABLE I.

Names of compounds.	<i>h. m.</i>											
Dichloromalon-di-phenylamide.	0:15	0:30	0:45	1:0	1:15	1:30	1:45	2:0	2:15	2:30	2:45	2:55
Dichloromalon-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide.	20:00	27:50	35:50	43:50	48:75	53:12	56:25	59:25	61:50	63:75	65:00	67:50
Dichloromalon-di- <i>m</i> -tolylamide-dichloride.	21:25	30:00	38:75	46:25	53:75	58:25	61:75	63:75	65:00	67:50	69:00	71:00
Dichloromalon-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide.	15:00	25:75	33:75	41:75	47:50	51:25	54:50	57:50	60:75	63:75	66:75	69:75
Dichloromalon-di-1:3:4-xylylide.	9:25	14:25	20:00	25:00	28:75	32:50	36:75	41:25	45:75	48:25	51:25	54:25
Dichloromalon-di- <i>n</i> -propylamide.	17:50	26:25	32:50	36:88	43:75	47:75	51:25	54:37	56:25	58:25	60:00	62:50
Dichloromalon-di-bethylamide.	23:75	31:25	39:40	45:62	51:25	55:50	60:00	63:75	67:50	70:00	72:50	75:00
Dichloromalon-di-propylamide.	15:00	21:25	26:25	30:75	36:00	40:75	45:00	48:75	51:85	54:75	57:50	60:75
Dichloromalon-mono- <i>p</i> -tolylamide.	10:00	17:50	25:75	29:25	34:50	38:50	42:00	45:50	48:75	51:25	53:75	56:25
Dichloromalon-mono-chlorophenylamide.	10:00	15:00	18:75	22:50	26:25	28:25	30:00	31:15	32:75	34:00	35:00	36:00
Chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-phenylamide.	11:50	17:50	21:87	25:75	30:00	32:50	35:00	37:00	38:00	39:00	40:00	41:00
Chloromethyl-chloromalon-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide.	18:75	26:25	31:25	35:00	39:25	43:75	48:00	51:25	53:75	56:25	58:75	61:25
Chloromethyl-chloromalon-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide.	7:50	12:50	18:10	21:75	25:00	27:50	30:00	32:50	34:50	36:00	37:50	39:50

% Saponified during the time shown in the column at the top of the Table.

In Fig. 4 are shown the curves for the saponification of (1) malon-di-heptylamide, (2) malon-di-phenylamide, (3) malon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (4) malon-di-*m*-tolylamide and (5) malon-di-*p*-tolylamide. In the first place the remarkable difference between the velocity of saponification of the amides of malonic acid on one hand and that of the chloro-derivatives on the other (*vide* Figs. 1), may be attributed to the transformation of the methylene group CH_2 into CCl_2 group of the substituted amides. Such a transformation must profoundly change the nature of the molecule. When the molecule undergoes a change, the initial condition is altered. Consequently the chemical activity of the imino group may also be altered.

They found that in the case of three malon di-tolylamides, the augmentation of the velocity of saponification proceeds as *para* $\rightarrow$ *meta* $\rightarrow$ *ortho*, which is in exact opposition to the velocity of saponification of their dichloro derivatives, for in the latter case it proceeds as *ortho* $\rightarrow$ *meta* $\rightarrow$ *para*. This apparent anomaly could be explained by the fact that the amides are capable of existing in a condition of tautomeric equilibrium in which the dichloro derivatives cannot. When in the case of chloro derivatives such dynamic isomerism is not easily possible, the velocity may be solely influenced by the position of the methyl group with regard to the saponifiable imino group as has already been mentioned.

Finally the results of the observations discussed above may be presented as follows:—

(1) The velocity of saponification of chloro derivatives is in full accord with their absorption spectra.

(2) The velocity of saponification depends upon the nature of the radical attached to the saponifiable imino grouping.

(3) In the case of chloro derivatives of malon-di-tolylamides, the velocity of saponification depends upon the position of the methyl group with regard to the saponifiable imino grouping.

(4) The transformation of methylene CH_2 group into CCl_2 group, enhances the absorption in the ultraviolet as also the chemical activity of the molecules, as expressed by the velocity of saponification, which is in accordance with the observation of Ramart, Naik and Trivedi (*loc. cit.*).